

Factorials: Difference between 0! and 1!

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Abstract: This paper discusses the difference between $0!=1$ and $1!=1$ for our understanding and also the usage of $0!$ in the mathematical function and series.

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1. Introduction

The factorial for a positive integer n , denoted by $n!$, is defined as the product of all positive integers less than or equal to n . For example, $5! = 1 \times 2 \times 3 \times 4 \times 5 = 720$. From this definition of the factorial, it is understood that the value (product) of a factorial begins from the integer 1. The factorial of the integer 0, denoted by $0!$, is used as 1 for our convenience. In general, $0!$ is not used in the product of positive integers, but it is used in a mathematical function and series obviously.

2. Difference between 0! and 1!

$1! = 1$ is entirely different from $0! = 1$. Let $f_n(x) = n! x^n$ for $n = 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, \dots$. Then $f_0(x) = 0! x^0 = 1$, $f_1(x) = 1! x^1 = x$, and so on. Similarly, let us assume that $g(x) = \sum_{i=0}^n i! x^i$. Then, $g(x) = 0! x^0 + 1! x^1 + 2! x^2 + 3! x^3 + 4! x^4 + \dots + n! x^n$. It is hereby understood that $0!$ is used in the mathematical function $f(x)$ and series $g(x)$ plainly. So, the factorial of the integer 0 is used as 1 for our convenience.

Note that there is no definition for negative factorial and binomial coefficient because both are positive integer or non-negative integer.

3. Conclusion

In this article, the difference between $0!$ and $1!$ have been discussed for our understanding. $0!$ was used in the mathematical function and series purposefully.

References

- [1] Annamalai, C. (2022) Factorial Theorem and Factorial for Non-Negative Real Number. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4376857>.
- [2] Annamalai, C. (2022) Factorials, Integers, and Factorial Theorems for Computing and Cryptography. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4189241>.